

Personal Income	279,771
Net Savings	26,426
Real Estate	244,313
Other Assets	7,380
Bank Accounts	844,379
Life Insurance	237,667
Individual Savings	563,560
Other Assets	45,000
Investment Account	461,771
Debt	103,700
Other Assets	278,981
Resources	4,567,284

What are you the experienced type? Or do you offer a high-end, high-quality product or a low-cost product? It's to be both. You should consider on thinking what your customers need you to be. Your logo is the main foundation of your brand. All the promotional materi-

Market Strategy

Marketing strategy goal is to increase sales and achieve advantage over other competitors. It includes short-term and long-term activities of marketing that has to do with the of a company's situation and contribute to its objectives. The objectives will be based on how you gain sales by acquiring and keeping customers. A marketing strategy helps on good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets, etc.

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Putting your strategy into action is how your marketing plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you how you're going to work with your targets. It may be through networking, advertising etc. Having the perfect timing with your activities to fit your customers buying cycles will help you saving money and maximizing sales. The marketing plan should be innovative. It should have the details on how your sales are followed up and the activities you doing to develop your offers.

It is a process to allow an organization to focus resources on the greatest opportunities to increase sales and achieve the company's target. Marketing strategy's goal is to increase sales and achieve the advantage over other competitors.

31.86%	30.23%	37.91%
UNIT ITEMS 12 500	UNIT ITEMS 12 500	UNIT ITEMS 12 500
SHIPPING 0.200	SHIPPING 0.200	SHIPPING 0.200
TOTAL 12.700	TOTAL 12.700	TOTAL 12.700

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ECONOMY OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

WORLD BANK'S STOCK AT ALL-TIME HIGH / US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOW

US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOW

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Industry and economy

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THE WORLD IS MESSSED UP BUT I BELIEVE WE ARE IN A POSITION NOW TO GET IT

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Framing the largest recent Romanian protests:

a content analysis of European online newspapers

Meda Mucundorfeanu⁴

Abstract

At the beginning of 2017 massive protests took place on the streets of the biggest cities in Romania, unprecedented in the post-communist history of the country.

They were caused by a decree passed by the government, which was meant to decriminalize certain offences, including politicians' abuse of office. The political situation and the protests came to the attention of the international press, who covered the story extensively. In this study, we analyze the way in which news media framed the largest Romanian protests since the fall of communism, to see how these events were depicted especially in other European countries, EU member states, in an attempt

to understand the emergence and development of public attitudes towards Romanian politics.

Our analysis included the twenty most read European online newspapers and the five most read Romanian newspapers, during the period of the protests, January 18th – March 5th 2017. We investigated the existence of five general news frames identified in specialized literature on media framing and framing effects (Semetko and Valkenburg, 2000): attribution of responsibility, conflict, human interest, economic consequences, and morality. Findings show that the Western European press framed the events predominantly from a human interest perspective, while the Romanian press depicted them in a more conflictual way. The use of news frames also varied significantly by type of outlet, with tabloid newspapers focusing more on the human interest frame, while the attribution of responsibility and the conflict frames were more present in quality newspapers.

Keywords: Corruption, Political Protest, Media Coverage, Generic Framing

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1. Introduction

Protests are an important means in contemporary societies through which citizens express their concerns and formulate their demands from the elected officials. The capability of successfully communicating their needs and achieving their goals depends on whether and how the media portray them (Lee, 2014).

Social movement groups often resort to marches, rallies or demonstrations in order to attract media attention and use it as a means of reaching the general public and the political institutions. However, on the one hand media attention is not guaranteed (Boyle et al., 2005), and on the other hand, those who manage to get the attention of the media can rarely exercise much control over the stories and perspective of the coverage (Entman and Rojecki, 1993) or the way their claims are represented in the media (Gamson and Modigliani, 1989). The probability of international coverage of a protest is significantly higher if at least 10,000 people participate in the event, if the protest takes place in the capital of a country (Herkenrath and Knoll, 2011) or if it involves marching (Lee, 2014), conditions which applied in the case of the Romanian protests further depicted.

The aforementioned protests were triggered by the attempt of the freshly appointed Romanian government to decriminalize several corruption offences through two emergency ordinances at the beginning of 2017.

This attempt prompted the largest display of popular anger since the fall of communism in 1989, with at least half a million people taking to the streets during its peak (Mucundorfeanu, 2019). A high proportion of students participated in the protests, much higher than during the demonstrations two years before, especially due to the fact that they searched for and retrieved political information online (Mercea, Burean and Protesa, 2020) and because of their high level of trust in the National Anti-Corruption Agency (Burean, 2019). The aim of the aforementioned decrees was to change the Romanian judicial system by modifying criminal law and redefining the crime of abuse of office. The opposition, anti-corruption prosecutors, magistrates and the Romanian protesters claimed that the ordinances were tailor-made to amnesty dozens of politically affiliated public officials convicted or accused of abuse of office.

All these events took place in a time when Romania's legal system was kept under special monitoring by the European Commission. Transparency International ranked Romania among the EU's most corrupt states. Romania ranked below all but three of its fellow EU states in a report based on the public perception of the prevalence of corruption⁵. In this context, Romania's long fight against corruption and its rule of law could have been threatened and undermined by the decrees, consequently the topic was highly publicized, both at a national and at an international level.

Romania was admitted to the EU in 2007 under the condition that it needed reforms in areas such as fighting crime, corruption and building an independent judiciary system. Starting then, Brussels imposed special monitoring procedures to ensure progress continued.

⁵ Corruption Perceptions Index (2018).

Available at: <https://www.transparency.org.ro/book/CPI2018/4/#zoom=z> (accessed 30 July 2019)

Before 2017, Romania had shown success in tackling graft, through its national anti-corruption directorate (DNA), which pursued officials regardless of their status. The recent draft amendments to the criminal code came to the attention of the international media especially due to the protests. The protests, as well as the aspects which triggered them, were covered by the media extensively. The governments of other member states of the EU regarded the situation in Romania as a great risk for the progress of the country in its fight against corruption. The European Commission criticized the proposed emergency ordinances and regarded them as an attempt to undermine the rule of law.

During the last 30 years, corruption has developed and spread across the country, which has impacted several areas, such as the economic, social or educational evolution of the Romanian society, fostering a feeling of distrust in the public institutions and in the business environment. The corruption phenomenon affects Romania, especially regarding the business field by diminishing the confidence of foreign investors in the potential of the country (Nițu, Paraschiv and Gheorghe, 2020). The aforementioned protests can be viewed as a symbol of changes in the democratic progress and the involvement of citizens can be considered to be a political instrument against non-democratic actions (Nicula et al., 2020).

In recent years, the international media coverage about Romania has been very often in the context of corruption (Balaban et al., 2021). The news coverage could have affected the way citizens of the EU viewed the Romanian government, Romanian politics, but also Romania as a member state of the EU. Consequently, coverage on this issue is crucial, although research (Lecheler and de Vreese, 2010) indicates that exposure to news frames has considerable impact on people's beliefs about the European integration of a country, but this effect is moderated by the political knowledge of the audience. Individuals with low political knowledge are more affected by frames than those better-informed. With respect to the duration of the effects of frames, research (Lecheler and de Vreese, 2011) shows that frames are surprisingly persistent, the duration of framing effects depending on a person's level of political knowledge, with moderately knowledgeable individuals displaying most persistent framing effects. Therefore, the perspective used in the coverage of the Romanian protests could have high and persistent effects especially on the opinions of individuals with moderate to little political knowledge. This might affect Romania's image and its efforts during the process of European integration. This process can be partially influenced by the way the media shape and frame political issues or social movements, such as protests.

Source: unsplash.com. Photo by Chris Slupski.

2. Theoretical background

The media no longer simply render facts, but rather suggest to the audience ways to understand the news (Gamson and Modigliani, 1987). Journalists are the ones who decide which aspects to stress in a news story, how to frame certain issues and how to imbue social, political and other events with meaning, as they are not only news-shapers, but also action-shapers.

Frames are part of our culture, they guide the way the elite construct information, they affect the way journalists select their information, frames are manifest in media texts and they influence the cognitive paths of audiences (Matthes, 2011: 248). „Frames are parts of political arguments, journalistic norms and social movements’ discourse. They are alternative ways of defining issues, endogenous to the political and social world.” (de Vreese, 2005: 53). According to Iyengar (1991) the exposure to news frames can influence audience members’ attributions of responsibility for problems, determine the readers’ beliefs, while Gross and Brewer (2007) claim that certain frames can influence the readers’ emotional responses. Framing can operate directly, affecting people’s beliefs, but also indirectly by offering new considerations or links between assessments, which had not existed before (de Vreese, Boomgarden and Semetko, 2010).

Scholars have found that both television and newspapers can contribute to political knowledge (Sotirovic and McLeod, 2004), but that newspaper readers are more informed than television viewers (Robinson and Davis, 1990).

Framing has been widely used by researchers in order to understand how citizens make sense of political, social, and economic issues (Slothuss and de Vreese, 2010). There is a variety of definitions regarding framing and frames, all with similar characteristics. From the standpoint of media content creators, “to frame is to select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation.” (Entman, 1993: 52). From the audience’s standpoint, news frames are “conceptual tools which media and individuals rely on to convey, interpret and evaluate information.” (Neuman et al., 1992, 60). According to Goffmann (1974: 21), human beings create the meaning of the world around them by organizing their experiences in particular frames, which allow them to “locate, perceive, identify, and label a seemingly infinite number of items of information.”

The first topic researched by scholars drawing on the framing concept was on how mass-media framed the social movements of the 60s (Benford and Snow, 2000). Framing is particularly helpful for understanding the effects of news media content for issues that are subjected to different presentations and interpretations (de Vreese, Boomgarden and Semetko, 2010).

There is vast evidence that news frames can decrease or increase the salience of an issue or consideration when citizens form their political opinions (de Vreese, 2004a; Matthes, 2008) and there is also evidence that attitudes towards political issues are shaped by frames consisting of strong arguments, such as compelling and convincing facts, or frames appealing to emotions such as fear or anger (Chong and Druckman, 2007).

The present study focuses on news frames, which are created by journalists and are usually shaped by journalistic values and norms, but also by the economics of the news business (Price and Tewksbury, 1997). Literature on media framing distinguishes between issue-specific media frames, which can be used to examine a topic in great detail, mostly through qualitative research, and generic news frames that are broader and can be used to examine various topics over time and across different cultures and media types. However, a news frames analysis through an issue-specific approach is difficult to generalize, compare, and use as a basis for a general hypothesis or theory building. Generic frames transcend thematic limitations, allow comparisons between frames and framing practices in different countries (De Vreese et al., 2001).

Although there are already many studies that use generic frames to present the coverage of an event, in Romania they have only been used to analyze the news coverage of electoral campaigns (Boțan and Corbu, 2011), the economic crisis (Radu and Ștefăniță, 2012), other European issues (Corbu et al., 2015) or the refugee crisis (Corbu et al., 2017). None of these studies included an overview of the coverage in national and foreign press. The novelty, therefore, is that this paper offers an image regarding both the framing of protests and a critical overview of the media coverage in different media types and countries.

This explains our choice of generic frames, which render cross-national differences visible. In order to assess which frames were predominantly used in the news stories regarding the Romanian protests, we used an adapted version of the scale from Semetko and Valkenburg (2000). Five generic frames were measured, which included a total of 18 questions that could be answered with yes or no. One of the advantages of using binary coding strategies is that in such cases the intercoder reliabilities are relatively high (Semetko and Valkenburg, 2000). The generic frames are the following: attribution of responsibility, human interest, conflict, morality and economic frame. The correspondent scales can be found in Appendix 1.

In this article, we analyze the way in which the media framed the aforementioned Romanian protests, to see how these events were depicted especially in other European countries, EU member states. Our theoretical interest was to analyze the coverage of the Romanian protests from 2017, to compare the use of frames in the most popular Romanian and European newspapers and to consider whether there are important differences between the regions corresponding to the selected newspapers (Romania vs. South Europe vs. Western Europe) and within the three regions corresponding to the selected newspapers (quality vs. sensationalist newspapers).

The effects of exposure to human interest and conflict frames in the news on political knowledge have been studied and are consistent across all media systems, irrespective of context (Jebril et al., 2013). According to Jebril and his colleagues (2013), exposure to conflict and human interest frames in political news increases political knowledge gain, but is moderated by political interest.

It is noteworthy that for those with a lower level of political interest, knowledge attainment is highest after exposure to the two frames and that exposure to the two frames has a smaller effect on political knowledge change (Jebril et al., 2013). We can argue that most readers from abroad, but also many Romanians with a lower level of political interest learned about the critical situation during the protests in Romania through the media coverage and shaped their interpretation of the topic in accordance with the presented perspectives, which can have an effect on their opinions and attitudes towards the Romanian government, politics, people and the country as a whole. Furthermore, exposure to the conflict frame can even boost political participation (De Vreese and Tobiason, 2007). This could be one explanation for the reason why Romanian citizens participated in the protests in such large numbers and the issue was so debated both at a national and an international level.

Previous research (DeVreese, Peter and Semetko, 2001) shows that the use of the conflict frame is considered to be a journalistic tradition mostly in Western democracies, being prevalent in journalistic articles published in Western European countries. Consequently, we formulate the following research question:

RQ1: Does the use of news frames vary significantly by region?

Previous research indicates that it is common for the human interest frame to be used by soft journalism (Jebril et al., 2013: 217), since it is a way of ensuring that complex issues reach the public, by using entertainment elements (Van Djik, 1988) or a human example (Iyengar, 1991). Consequently, we formulate the following research question:

RQ2: Does the use of news frames vary significantly by type of outlet (qualitative vs. tabloid)?

Source: unsplash.com. Photo by Arun Sharma.

3. Methodology

The newspaper articles were analyzed during the time frame 18.01.2017 - 05.03.2017, which corresponds to the period when the protests took place. The analysis included the two most read quality online newspapers, *Adevărul* and *Evenimentul zilei*, the two most read tabloid online newspapers, *Click* and *Cancan* and the most used news platform, *hotnews.ro* in Romania, according to the *Romanian Transmedia Audit Bureau*, which registers Internet traffic and audience.

Regarding the European newspapers, we chose the top 20 most read online newspapers in Europe, 18 of which covered the story of the Romanian protests, but only 17 were selected for the analysis, because the newspaper from Poland (*Gazeta Wyborcza*) covered the topic just twice. The ranking was created by the website *4 International Media & Newspapers*, which is an international directory and search engine focusing on worldwide newspapers, containing 7,000 newspapers from 200 countries, ranked by web popularity.

The ranking is based on an algorithm which includes four unbiased and independent web metrics extracted from four different search engines: Google Page Rank, Alexa Traffic Rank, Majestic Seo Referring Subnets and Majestic Seo Trust Flow.⁶

The international newspapers were the following: from Great Britain: *The Guardian*, *The Daily Mail*, *The Daily Telegraph*, *The Independent*, *Financial Times*, *Daily Express*; from Germany: *Bild*, *Die Welt*, *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, *die Zeit*; from France: *Le Monde*, *Le Figaro*, from Spain: *El País*, *El Mundo*, *ABC*; from Italy: *La Repubblica* and *Corriere della Sera*.

For a better overview we grouped the international newspapers into two regions: Italy and Spain were grouped into *South Europe* (n=47 articles), Great Britain, Germany and France were grouped into *Western Europe* (n=195 articles). We compared the newspapers in these regions with those from Romania (n=161 articles).

A total number of 403 news stories were coded (N=403) from all 22 newspapers. All international articles related to the Romanian protests were included in the sample. Regarding the Romanian articles, where the story was highly publicized, we created an artificial week and included in the sample those articles on the topic of protests, which appeared in the five Romanian newspapers, as follows: all articles published on the Monday of the first week of the protests, followed by all articles published on the Tuesday of the second week of the protests, and so on, until the end of the sixth week.

Coding was performed manually by the author and by a former student of the department. Both coders are fluent in Romanian, English and German and have a good command of the other Romance languages. The coders were instructed to code for the presence (1) or absence (0) of the variables under investigation.

⁶ Newspaper Web Rankings. Available at: <https://www.4imn.com/> (accessed 07 January 2019)

To determine the intercoder reliability, a random sample of 10% of the total number of articles ($n = 403$) was analyzed. This is consistent with the recommendation of calculating the intercoder reliability on a subsample between 10-20% of the total sample (Weathers et al., 2014). Krippendorff's alpha was used for the calculation. The reliability coefficient for the analyzed category was .84. We chose this reliability measure because, according to its developers, Krippendorff's alpha can be used "regardless of the number of observers, levels of measurement, sample sizes, and presence or absence of missing data." (Hayes and Krippendorff, 2007: 77)

We used an adapted version of the scale from Semetko and Valkenburg (2000) in order to assess which frames were predominantly used in the news stories regarding the Romanian protests. Five generic frames were measured, as follows: attribution of responsibility, human interest conflict, morality and economic frame.

Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated in order to measure the internal consistency for the five scales values. Results indicated that the scales were reliable: the attribution of responsibility frame consisting of 3 items ($\alpha = .97$), the human interest frame with 5 items ($\alpha = .92$), the conflict frame with 4 items ($\alpha = .95$), the morality frame with 3 items ($\alpha = .96$) and the economic frame with 3 items ($\alpha = .98$).

4. Results

The general characteristics of the coverage in all seven countries are listed in Table 1. Most of the articles (37% of articles) used the human interest frame, followed by the attribution of responsibility frame (in 30% of the articles) and the conflict frame (in 20% of articles). The least present frames are the morality (in 10.7% of articles) and the economic frame (in 1.7% of articles).

Table 1: Distribution of frames (numbers and percentages) in articles, by country.

	Attribution of Responsibility Frame	Human Interest Frame	Conflict Frame	Morality Frame	Economic Frame
Romania	46	51	46	15	2
Great Britain	33	45	8	18	4
Germany	18	28	16	5	1
Spain	9	14	5	1	0
Italy	6	6	2	4	0
France	9	7	4	0	0
Total/frame	121 (30%)	151 (37.5%)	81 (20%)	43 (10.7%)	7 (1.7%)

Table 2 shows that the most dominant frames are the human interest (M= .29) and the attribution of responsibility frame (M= .28). Although we are talking about protests, the conflict frame (M= .17) does not seem to be as important as the responsibility frame. It seems the focus of the coverage lies on finding the guilty actors, on directing the blame towards someone or on finding a scapegoat. The only place where conflict plays an important role is in the Romanian press, which often depicted the involved political actors in situations where they were blaming each other.

It seems that the Romanian journalists have tried to educate the public about the problem, by mostly using the attribution of responsibility frame (M= .27), while the international journalists tried to attract the attention of the audience towards this issue and have depicted the news in a more personalized and emotional way. The human interest frame was the most common frame used in news articles from Western (M= .34) and South Europe (M= .33).

Table 2: Intensity of frames by region of the outlets, for news stories about the protests in Romania.

Region		Attribution of Responsibility Frame	Human Interest Frame	Conflict Frame	Morality Frame	Economic Frame
Romania	Mean	.27	.23	.24	.07	.01
	N.	161	161	161	161	161
	Std. Deviation	.43	.35	.39	.24	.11
Western Europe	Mean	.29	.34	.12	.11	.02
	N.	195	195	195	195	195
	Std. Deviation	.44	.42	.31	.31	.14
South Europe	Mean	.26	.33	.11	.09	.00
	N.	47	47	47	47	47
	Std. Deviation	.42	.41	.28	.29	.00
Total	Mean	.28	.29	.17	.09	.01
	N.	403	403	403	403	403
	Std. Deviation	.43	.40	.35	.28	.12

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to answer RQ1, which examined the difference between the three regions (Romania, South and Western Europe) regarding the use of the five frames.

We found no difference between how media outlets in different countries covered the story in terms of responsibility ($F(2, 403)=.028, p=.86, \eta^2=.001$), morality frame ($F(2, 403)=.069, p=.437, \eta^2=.004$), and economic consequences ($F(2, 403)=.013, p=.436, \eta^2=.004$), but the stories differ in terms of human interest ($F(2, 403)=.532, p=.036, \eta^2=.017$) and conflict dimensions ($F(2, 403)=.728, p=.003, \eta^2=.029$) between Romania and Western Europe. The Western European newspapers framed the story mostly in terms of human interest, while the Romanian ones framed it in terms of conflict.

Table 2: Distribution of frames (numbers and percentages) in articles, by type of outlet.

	Attribution of Responsibility Frame	Human Interest Frame	Conflict Frame	Morality Frame	Economic Frame	Total
Quality newspapers	88 (35.8%)	63 (25.6%)	62 (25.2%)	30 (12.2%)	3 (1.2%)	246 (61%)
Tabloid newspapers	35 (22.3%)	88 (56%)	17 (10.85%)	13 (8.3%)	4 (2.55%)	157 (39%)

The general characteristics of the coverage in quality (n=246 articles) versus tabloid newspapers (n=157 articles) are depicted in Table 3. Most of the articles stemmed from quality newspapers (61%), compared to tabloid newspapers (39%). The former predominantly used the attribution of responsibility frame (35.8% of quality news articles), while the latter mostly used the human interest frame (56% of tabloid news articles). To be more precise, table 3 shows that 35.8% of all articles published in quality newspapers used the attribution of responsibility frame, while 56% of all tabloid articles used the human interest frame.

Source: unsplash.com. Photo by Aj Colores

Table 4 shows that the most dominant interest in quality newspapers was to find the responsible actors and it was secondary to them to show the audience various political leaders blaming each other or to present individual dramas caused by the decree. The tabloid newspapers aimed at reaching the audiences' attention by emphasizing the emotional aspects of the events.

Table 3: Intensity of frames by type of outlet for news stories about the protests in Romania.

Type of outlet		Attribution of Responsibility Frame	Human Interest Frame	Conflict Frame	Morality Frame	Economic Frame
Quality	Mean	.33	.20	.22	.11	.01
	N.	246	246	246	246	246
	Std. Deviation	.45	.35	.38	.30	.09
Tabloid	Mean	.21	.44	.09	.07	.02
	N.	157	157	157	157	157
	Std. Deviation	.39	.41	.27	.25	.15
Total	Mean	.27	.32	.15	.09	.01
	N.	403	403	403	403	403
	Std. Deviation	.42	.38	.32	.27	.12

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to answer RQ2, which examined the difference between quality papers and tabloids in their use of the five frames.

There was a significant difference between quality papers and tabloids regarding the use of the attribution of responsibility frame $t(365.226)=2.77$, $p=.006$, the use of the human interest frame $t(293.23)=-6.15$, $p<.001$ and the use of the conflict frame $t(394.03)=3.87$, $p<.001$.

There was no significant difference between quality papers and tabloids regarding the use of the morality frame $t(401)=-1.340$, $p=.181$ and the use of the economic frame $t(401)=-1.42$, $p=.254$.

These results are proof of journalistic routines which influence the outcome of journalists' work, but the nature of the events also plays an important role in determining the dominant frames.

4. Discussion

Since the particular framing of an issue influences public opinion towards that issue, the aim of our study was to provide insights into the ways in which the news media approached the topic of the protests in Romania.

We used an adapted version of the Semetko and Valkenburg questionnaire, consisting of 18 framing questions to empirically assess the five most common news frames discussed in specialized literature. Our framing items showed a satisfactory intercoder reliability as well as a satisfactory internal consistency. We studied the prevalence of these frames in four national newspapers, one national news website, and in 17 international, European newspapers (N=430 articles).

The extensive coverage of this topic by the national, as well as by the international media can be explained through the fact that such an ample response to acts of corruption raises the attention and is of interest for people in general and for individual entities who have a direct or indirect (economic, social, etc.) interest in the country. The topic is especially interesting for the media because it comprises several fundamental news values, according to the classic operationalization of news values conducted by Galtung and Ruge (1965), such as: threshold, meaningfulness, unexpectedness, and of course negativity.

By its very nature, a content analysis cannot determine the effect media frames have on the public, nevertheless several key findings emerged from this analysis, which can be corroborated with the findings of previous research. Overall, the most common frames were, in order of predominance: human interest, attribution of responsibility, conflict, morality and economic consequences. The use of two of the news frames varied significantly by region, especially between Romania and Western Europe, the human interest frame being predominantly used in Western Europe and the conflict frame predominantly in Romania. The use of news frames also varied significantly by type of outlet (quality vs. tabloid papers), the human interest frame being more present in tabloid newspapers, while the attribution of responsibility and the conflict frame were more present in quality newspapers.

Our expectation was that the protests would be depicted in Romania rather in a sensationalistic manner (human interest frame), because in Romania, after the fall of communism, the fact that media consumption has constantly risen and the media is mostly privately owned, has generated relentless search for sensationalism (Balaban, 2007).

The human interest frame brings a human face or emphasizes the emotional angle of an event. Neuman et al. (1992) described this as the “human impact” frame, and, next to conflict, found it to be a common frame in the news. Such a frame refers to an effort to personalize the news, dramatize or “emotionalize” the news, in order to capture and retain the audience’s interest (Semetko and Valkenburg, 2000).

The topic of the Romanian protests was rendered mostly from this perspective across all sources. The media often focused on one specific protester (e.g. an elderly person, a parent, a freelancer) and their story in order to create a feeling of empathy, felt at least by the readers who were in the same situation. This type of frame was especially evident in tabloid newspapers. The prevalence of this frame was also observed in studies on sensitive issues, where the fate of millions of people was at stake, such as asylum seekers (d'Haenens and de Lange, 2001) or irregular immigration - where the human interest frame was present in almost half of the news coverage on irregular immigration in Norway, France and the US from January 2011 through June 2012 (Aalberg and Beyer, 2015).

The conflict frame emphasizes disagreements between individuals, groups, or institutions as a means of capturing the audience's interest. According to DeVreese and his colleagues (DeVreese, Peter and Semetko, 2001), emphasizing the conflict-related aspects of an issue by framing it in terms of conflict may justify the publication of a news story above and beyond its intrinsic news value. Different from the outcome of previous research (DeVreese, Peter and Semetko, 2001), our findings show that the conflict frame was prevalent in the articles published in Romania. Previous studies have observed that published contradictory discussions between political elites often reduce complex substantive political debates to overly simplistic conflict and therefore manage to gain the attention of the audience (Semetko and Valkenburg, 2000).

Our findings indicate that the online media outlets we analyzed also framed the Romanian protests in terms of accountability. The responsibility frame was prevalent across all sources and was especially evident in quality newspapers.

According to our framing questions, responsibility was attributed explicitly to the Romanian government, which had been the initiator of the decree that prompted the largest display of popular anger since the fall of communism.

In line with previous research (Matthes, 2009), we note that attributions of responsibility depend not only on the mass media's framing, but also on the general attributional preferences of the readers, especially with regard to thematic framing. Nevertheless, the more judgment-relevant information a news frame provides, the more readers will base their attributional judgements on the news frame and less on their general personality traits (Matthes, 2009). In this particular case, the remarks formulated by the media regarding accountability for the problem were very detailed and explicit.

Journalists were least preoccupied with the economic and morality frame. Which is in line with other framing research on Romanian media outlets, where the researcher explained this by mentioning the public's lack of interest in the arid economy-related topics. (Corbu et al., 2017). The economic frame reports an event in terms of the economic consequences it will have on an individual, group, institution, region, or country. Previous research has demonstrated that the use of the conflict and economic frames has the ability to influence the direction of the audience's thoughts when reflecting upon a contemporary political issue (de Vreese, 2004b). The last frame was not predominant. The morality frame puts the event in the context of moral prescriptions. In the present case this was done indirectly, by quoting others referring to this aspect.

Specialized literature includes several similar studies on generic framing.

Some of them focus on the introduction of the common European currency, the euro (de Vreese, Peter and Semetko, 2001), on protests against the gas exploitation of a company (Coman and Cmeciu, 2014), on the migration crisis in the Canary Islands (Diaz and Montes, 2008) or on asylum seekers in the world, covered by the press from the Netherlands (d'Haenens and de Lange, 2001). The originality of our study lies in the fact that it attempts to render a broader picture, by focusing on the coverage of a topic in national, as well as in the international press, and also by comparing the coverage of the topic in quality and tabloid press.

5. Conclusions and limitations

The fight against corruption has been a central theme in Romania's public sphere since the mid-2000s and has been frequently the trigger for protests against corrupt public actors and institutions.

Domestic incentives, such as the active involvement of citizens in combating corruption, as well as pressure from the EU institutions through sanctions, have contributed to progress in the fight against corruption and have deepened Romania's European integration (Spendzharova and Vachudova, 2012). Therefore, it is important to see how the media has portrayed these protests, as media coverage can contribute to the understanding and reaction of the EU institutions and citizens towards tensed situations that Romania is facing.

The empirical analysis of protest events and other expressions of social conflict is one of the core tasks of the discipline of comparative sociology (Herkenrath and Knoll, 2011), but also of neighboring fields, such as (political) communication and media studies. To our knowledge, our study is one of the few that considered the ways in which journalists emphasized certain perspectives (frames) in their reporting about

political protests, by using the binary coding system developed by Semetko and Valkenburg (2000) and it is one of the very few that conducted a cross-country comparison. The advantages of using such a system are explained in the first pages of the article. A cross-national framing analysis can be fruitful and render a bigger picture of the events, especially with respect to the extent to which factors internal and external to journalism, influence the emergence of frames in the news.

We recognize that one of the limitations of the present research, such as the sample is not a true representative sample of the regions discussed in this article. Although we took steps to include a diverse array of newspapers from within the given regions, the newspapers used in this sample are the 17 most read European newspapers, which stem from just 5 countries, plus the 5 most read news outlets from Romania. However, this still allows for important insights into differences across cultures and regions to be gained. Beyond that, the consistency of the findings across cultures is supported by previous research. Future research ought to extend news coverage of the protest beyond the top 20 most read newspapers.

Third, the descriptive nature of the study requires further research focusing on the mobilization factors behind the protests and on the effects of the media frames which have been used by the media.

Our main contribution lays in identifying differences and similarities in frames across different types of news media belonging to different European countries and regions with regard to news coverage about protests. It is our hope that this study will shed some light onto how the Romanian protests were presented by the media and shaped the public's interpretation of the events and serve as a catalyst for further research on protests in European media and not only. Especially the international coverage of this topic can greatly affect the way Romania is being viewed by citizens of the EU and also by foreign investors, since corruption can impair a country's economic as well as social fields.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Adapted framing scale after Semetko & Valkenburg (2000)

Attribution of responsibility frame

- Does the story suggest that the government, political decision makers or parties are responsible?
- Does the story suggest solutions to the problem?
- Does the story suggest that the problem requires rapid/urgent actions?

Human Interest frame

- Does the story provide a human face, an individual example regarding the problem (protesters, other citizens, journalists, etc.)?
- Does the story refer to ordinary people's reactions to events?
- Does the story employ adjectives that might generate feelings of outrage, empathy, sympathy, or compassion?
- Does the story emphasize how individuals and groups are affected by the issue/problem?
- Does the story contain visual information that might generate feelings of outrage, empathy, sympathy, or compassion?

Conflict frame

- Does the story suggest conflicts/disagreements between parties/ groups/ individuals/ decision makers?
- Does the story refer to winners and losers?
- Does the story reflect that parties/ individuals/ decision makers/ countries reproach one another?
- Does the story refer to two sides of the problem?

Morality frame

- Does the story contain any moral message?
- Does the story refer to religious or other values (faith, solidarity, tenacity, honesty)?
- Does the story refer to specific social norms (e.g. civic duty) that should be adopted (are acceptable)?

Economic frame

- Does the story refer to financial losses or gains on the short or long term (for anyone)?
- Does the story mention costs or expenses?
- Does the story mention economic consequences of pursuing/ not pursuing a course of action?

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